

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	2010	B		Min: 63.2529 Max: 63.4436	1244 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 1356-1358 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: *crushed mbr floor in room?*
 Covered by SU: 1218 Fills SU: Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction
 FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive Compaction Color <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Soft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <i>orange</i>

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)
 Northern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original
 Southern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Western Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Eastern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts: 1299, relationship to 1183 unclear
Is covered by: 1218	Covers: n.a.
Is cut by: 1314, 1261, 1270, 1278	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS: *dry, hot conditions, excavated with bowel*

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: *very central in eastern part of area B 2010*
 Shape: *originally square, but no irregular through later truncation*

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): *slight slope to NW-corner*
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): *-*
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): *constant thickness of ca. 5-6 cm*
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commigled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:
 Cut edges: rounded straight
 Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping
 Cut bottom: flat concave irregular
 How is cut top edge? sharp rounded
 How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded
 Observations:

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify) *Crushed tufo*

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description: *very orange, very compacted tufo fragments of up to 5cm Ø. The tufo pieces seem to have been massively compacted without using a binding agent.*

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

See front

INTERPRETATION

Remains of the tufo floor in room 3

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	<i>CHM</i>	on	<i>03.08.2010</i>
Revised by	<i>CHM</i>	on	<i>03.08.2010</i>
PDFd by		on	
Entered by		on	